

A numerical analysis of the ultimate limit capacity of a riveted lap joint partially strengthened by high strength steel bolts

Oskar Skoglund^{*,a,b}, John Leander^b, Boulent Imam^c

^aBridge & Plant Design, ÅF-infrastructure AB, 169 75 Solna, Sweden

^bDivision of Structural Engineering and Bridges, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 100 44 Stockholm, Sweden

^c School of Sustainability, Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Surrey, Guildford GU2 7XH, UK
oskar.o.skoglund@afry.com & oskarsko@kth.se

ABSTRACT

Before the 1960s, the construction of steel bridges commonly involved the use of rivets. Nowadays, several of these riveted bridges that remain operational require strengthening to enhance their static strength and extend their projected lifespan in terms of fatigue. In many cases, the reinforcement approach involves replacing the rivets with high strength steel bolts. Neither the Eurocode nor the Swedish design regulations address joints that incorporate both rivets and bolts. A cautious approach is to consider the design strength to be dependent solely on the bolts within the joint, without taking into account the strength provided by the rivets. This article examines the static strength of a riveted lap joint that has been partially reinforced using high strength steel bolts through the use of detailed numerical analysis. The findings in the paper indicate that a lap joint made up of three rivets and a high-strength steel bolt exhibits similar or even greater strength with respect to shear connector and bearing pressure failure compared to the original configuration consisting of four rivets.

Keywords: Rivets, bolts, lap joint, strengthening

1 INTRODUCTION

Before the 1960s, the construction of steel bridges commonly involved the use of rivets. Nowadays, several of these riveted bridges that remain operational require strengthening. A common method to enhance the static and fatigue strength of riveted connections is by replacing rivets with high strength steel bolts. However, this replacement process can sometimes be challenging, as it may need to be carried out while the bridge is still operational, and not all rivets may be easily accessible for removal and replacement. As a result, in certain cases, the static strength of the bridge relies on connections that have a combination of rivets and high strength steel bolts. Neither the Eurocode nor the Swedish design regulations address joints that incorporate both rivets and bolts. A cautious approach is to consider the design strength to be dependent solely on the bolts within the joint, without taking into account the strength provided by the rivets. Numerous publications have studied riveted structures, as evidenced by reference (1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6). Among these studies, reference (1) focused on testing the ultimate limit strength of riveted lap joints. For this experiment, the specimens were produced using materials and techniques representative of 1950's standards, and they were tested in conjunction with the specimens' manufacturing process. Interestingly, the lap joints' strength exceeded the predictions made by the Eurocode design standard (7). This notable difference in strength is likely to be due to high rivet clamping forces generated during assembly.

In reference (6), the researchers measured clamping forces extracted from old bridges. They observed that the magnitude of clamping forces tends to decrease with a reduction in grip length and an increase in the number of plates. The clamping stresses measured ranged from approximately 25 to 150 MPa.

In this paper, nonlinear numerical analyses are performed on a riveted lap joint where one of the rivets is replaced by a high strength steel bolt. The ultimate limit strength and load distribution between the connecting elements are studied in detail. The aim of the paper is to give design recommendations for lap joints partially reinforced by high strength steel bolts.

2 NUMERICAL MODELLING APPROACH

A nonlinear numerical model of a lap joint is constructed using Abaqus 2022 as pre- and post-processor. Two types of nonlinearities are considered, namely, material and contact nonlinearity. The material models used for the rivets, base plate, and high strength bolt are given in *Fig. 1* (a) and (b). The material behaviour is taken from experimental studies in (1), (8) and (9), and incorporates a linear ductile damage model. The onset of damage is indicated by ϵ_0^{pl} .

Fig. 1. Material models used in the numerical analysis, (a) true stress strain curve obtained from (1) and (8), and (b) fracture strain as a function of stress triaxiality obtained from (9).

The numerical model is illustrated in *Fig. 2*, and consists of four connectors (c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4), initially comprising four rivets. One of the rivets is replaced by a pre-tensioned M16 high strength steel bolt and loaded to failure. The dimensions used in the numerical analyses are given in *Table 1*, the bolt hole clearance is set to 2 mm. The analysis comprises two sequential steps. Initially, clamping forces are applied to the connectors and in the subsequent step the external load is applied as a prescribed displacement. Two specimens are studied (S1 and S2), the main difference being the number of shear planes n . S1 is a single-shear joint with $n = 1$ and S2 is a double-shear joint with $n = 2$.

The contact conditions are formulated between the plates and rivets/bolt/washer constituting the connection. The contact condition is formulated with a normal and tangential behaviour component. The normal behaviour component, relating to pressure-overclosure, is formulated using a “hard” contact condition with a Lagrange enforcement method. The tangential behaviour is based on a penalty formulation and with a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$, unless otherwise specified. The connectors' shank and head/nut were modelled as a unified part, whereas the washers, employed for the bolt, were retained as separate parts. The contact surfaces are illustrated in *Fig. 3*.

The numerical model uses 8-node linear brick elements, with a mesh size of 2 mm for the connectors and in the plates adjacent to the connectors. The average aspect ratio of the mesh in the critical regions is 1.40 in the rivets/bolts and 1.25 in the plates. The clamping forces were added to the connectors through the Abaqus “Bolt load” function, which produces a pre-tension in the connectors. The “Bolt load” is schematically illustrated in *Fig. 2* (a) and the numerical model representing specimen S1 with a rivet replaced by a bolt is displayed in *Fig. 2* (b). The numerical models are validated against testing of riveted lap joints presented in (1).

Fig. 2. Illustrating the lap-joint and (a) how the pre-tensioning was applied to the connectors, and (b) the numerical model representing specimen S1 where rivet c_1 has been replaced by a high strength steel bolt (symmetry conditions are utilised).

Table 1. Giving the dimensions and number of shear planes used in the numerical models.

Specimen	t [mm]	d_r [mm]	d_b [mm]	l_1 [mm]	l_2 [mm]	r_1 [mm]	r_2 [mm]	p [mm]	n [-]
S1	10	16	14.1	40	250	35	45	60	1
S2	7	16	14.1	40	164	22	75	40	2

Fig. 3. Illustrating the contact conditions between connectors and the plates, and between the bolt shank/nut and the washers.

3 DESIGN ACCORDING TO THE EUROCODE

The numerical results are compared to what is being predicted with Eurocode design calculations (7), where partial coefficients have been disregarded. The shear capacity $F_{v,Rd}$ per shear plane of the connector is calculated as:

$$F_{v,Rd} = 0.6f_{ub}A \quad (1)$$

where f_{ub} is the ultimate limit strength and A is the cross-sectional area of the connector. Bearing capacity of the hole is calculated as:

$$F_{b,Rd} = k_1\alpha_b f_{up}dt \quad (2)$$

where k_1 and α_b are factors depending on the distance to the free edge and/or adjacent holes, and f_{up} is the ultimate limit strength of the plate.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Validation of the numerical modelling approach

Two experiments are used to validate the numerical modelling approach. The two lap joint configurations have similar denotations as in (1). No rivet hole clearance is added to the finite element model developed. The experiments in (1) cover rivet shear failure (U16-10-1) and bearing failure (S16-10-1). The results from the numerical analyses, the experimental studies in (1), and Eurocode calculations are presented in *Fig. 4*. The results are produced for two different values of friction coefficients, $\mu = 0.3$ and $\mu = 0.8$, and two different levels of clamping stresses. The differences in results between the experiment and the numerical analyses likely stem from variations in the material models presented in (1) for the rivets and plates, clamping stresses, and/or friction coefficient. The material data presented in *Fig. 1* (a) represent average values. As depicted in *Fig. 4*, the clamping stresses, σ_{clamp} , together with the friction coefficient play a crucial role in the overall behaviour. It is important to highlight that using a clamping stress of 300 MPa resulted in decreased capacity when utilising a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$ compared to using 0 MPa clamping stress. This decrease is attributed to the premature yielding of the rivet due to the clamping stress approaching the yield strength of the rivet material – compare the clamping stress with the yield strength of the material in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 4. Presenting the results for (a) specimen U16-10-1, and (b) specimen S16-10-1.

4.2 Study of the four connector specimens

This section presents the results of numerical analyses conducted on lap joints comprising four connectors, as depicted in *Fig. 2*. Pre-stressing forces in the rivets and rivet hole clearance has not been included in the results presented in the figures in this section. However, their effect has been studied and commented. A friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$ is used.

Fig. 5 (a) illustrates the ultimate limit strength of specimen S1 in its initial configuration and two cases where rivet c_1 , and c_2 have been replaced by a high strength steel bolt respectively. The initial configuration consists of four rivets. The high strength steel bolt is pre-tensioned by $F_{p,C} = 0.7f_{ub}A$. Specimen S1 fails through shear of the connectors, and a contour plot of the von Mises stresses before the onset of damage is illustrated in *Fig. 6* (a) and (b). The shear capacity of one high strength steel bolt is 75 kN. As can be seen from *Fig. 5* (a), the capacity of the strengthened connection is not solely relying on the strength of the bolt, but the load is being distributed among the connectors. Adding a high strength steel bolt to the connection has no impact on the shear capacity of the lap joint compared to its initial configuration. In the initial configuration, the shear force and the damage in the rivets are evenly distributed, see *Fig. 6* (c). In the strengthened case, the damage is localised in the rivets, see *Fig. 6* (d).

Fig. 5 (b) depicts the ultimate limit strength of specimen S2 in its initial configuration, and four cases where rivet c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , and c_4 have been replaced by a high strength steel bolt respectively. In all five cases, the specimen fails through bearing pressure around the rivet/bolt holes. The most critical bearing pressure is found around connector c_4 , as such, the most effective strengthening procedure is obtained by adding a pre-tensioned bolt at c_4 , where the pre-tensioning forces reduce the shear force transmitted through the bolt hole. The bolt comes into bearing at approximately 1.2 mm displacement, which gives a sudden increase in stiffness of the connection. The strength of the connection is greater for all strengthened cases, except for when rivet c_1 is replaced, for which it is 1.2 % lower. The von Mises stress distribution at the increment before the onset of damage and the distribution of damage at failure is presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. In the initial configuration, see Fig. 7, the stress distribution before the onset of damage is evenly distributed among the four rivet holes in the centre plate. However, as the load progresses, the rivet hole at connector c_4 starts to develop more damage than the other rivet holes due to a more severe triaxial stress state. In the case where connector c_4 is replaced by a high strength steel bolt, the triaxial stress state becomes less severe around hole c_4 and a lower amount of forces are transferred through bearing pressure at c_4 , which contributes to an increase in the capacity.

Fig. 5. Showing the ultimate limit capacity of specimen (a) S1 and (b) S2.

Fig. 6. Illustrating the von Mises stress for specimen S1 before the onset of damage for (a) the initial configuration and (b) when c_1 is replaced with a bolt, and damage in specimen S1 for (c) the initial configuration and (d) when c_1 is replaced with a bolt. 1.0 is equivalent to 100 % damage.

Fig. 7. Presenting specimen S2 in the initial configuration. The von Mises stress distribution before the onset of damage is presented in (a) for the whole specimen and (b) in the centre plate. The damage at failure in the centre plate is presented in (c).

Fig. 8. Presenting specimen S2 with c_4 replaced with a high strength steel bolt. The von Mises stress distribution before the onset of damage is presented in (a) for the whole specimen and (b) in the centre plate. The damage at failure in the centre plate is presented in (c).

The total shear force transferred in the four connectors for specimen S1 and S2 is presented in Fig. 9 — in specimen S1, rivet c_1 has been replaced, and in S2, rivet c_4 has been replaced by a high strength steel bolt. The high strength steel bolt in the single shear specimen S1 starts to transfer shear forces before the shank gets into contact with the steel plates, as can be seen in the blow-up in Fig. 9 (a). This does not occur in the double shear specimen S2, where the high strength steel bolt starts to transfer shear forces once it gets into contact with the centre plate. The amount of shear force transmitted through the different connectors depends on the bearing pressure capacity and the pre-tensioning forces. Initially, in specimen S1, rivet c_4 transfers a slightly higher shear force compared to c_2 and c_3 , this is because the plates at c_4 transfer the smallest amount of shear through friction. At yield, c_4 transfers a smaller amount of shear than the two other rivets, this is because of a premature development of damage caused by a small tensile component in the rivet that occurs in single shear joints.

Fig. 9. Showing the force distribution in the four connectors (c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4), when replacing, (a) rivet C_1 in specimen S1 and (b) rivet C_4 in specimen S2, by a high strength steel bolt. The contour plots are showing von Mises stresses.

As has been demonstrated by the numerical studies presented in Fig. 5, 6, 7 and 8. The capacity of the connection is not being reduced to any notable extent by replacing a rivet with a high strength steel bolt, quite contrary it can increase. However, if a rivet hole clearance is assumed, the slip resistance should be based on the high strength steel bolt alone. Adding a rivet hole clearance or a small pre-tensioning force does not affect the relative difference in ultimate limit capacity with respect to bearing pressure and connector shear capacity between joints in their initial and strengthened configuration to any large extent. Adding a rivet hole clearance of 0.6 mm reduced the ultimate limit strength in S2 (failure due to bearing pressure) by approximately 1 to 5 %, and did not affect the capacity of S1 (connector shear failure). In aged riveted structures, only a small clamping force can be expected, see reference (6). An initial clamping stress of 25 MPa added to the rivets did not affect the strength of the joint.

5 DISCUSSION

In the ultimate limit stage of riveted and bolted joints the connection is often assumed to mainly transfer shear forces. Therefore, the results produced herein can be applied to other riveted joints carrying their load predominantly in shear, which is applicable to many riveted and bolted connections in the ultimate limit state.

It should be noted that using a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$ is a conservative assumption. By assuming a higher friction coefficient, the benefits of replacing a rivet with a high strength steel bolt increases further.

6 CONCLUSIOS

This article investigates the static strength of a riveted lap joint that has been partially reinforced using high-strength steel bolts, studied through numerical analyses. Currently, there are no guidelines of how to address these scenarios. A conservative approach is to only consider the strength contribution of the high-strength steel bolt(s) while disregarding the contribution of the rivets. However, this article demonstrates that the ultimate limit strength capacity concerning bearing pressure and connector shear failure significantly surpasses the strength of the bolt(s) alone. The study conducted here indicates that joint design incorporating a combination of rivets and high-strength steel bolts are not significantly weaker than the original riveted connection that solely used rivets, quite contrary it can be far greater.

REFERENCES

1. *Experimental investigation on shear behaviour of riveted connections in steel structures.* **Aniello M.D., Portioli F., Fiorino L., and Landolfo R.** s.l. : Engineering Structures, 2011, Vol. 33.
2. *Fatigue Performance of Stringer-to-Floor-Beam Connections in Riveted Railway Bridges.* **Al-Emrani, M.** 10, s.l. : Journal of Bridge Engineering, 2005, Vol. 10.
3. **Chesson, E JR.** *Behavior of Large Riveted and Bolted Structural Connections (PhD dissertation).* s.l. : University of Illinois, 1959.
4. *Numerical modelling of riveted railway bridge connections for fatigue evaluation.* **Imam, B., Righiniotis, T.D., Chryssanthopoulos M. K.** s.l. : Engineering Structures, 2007, Vol. 29.
5. **Larsson, T.** *Fatigue assessment of riveted bridges (PhD dissertation).* Luleå : Luleå University of Technology, 2009.
6. *Rivet clamping force as-built hot-riveted connections in steel bridges.* **Leonetti, D., Maljaars, J., Pasquarelli, G. and Brando, G.** s.l. : Journal of Constructional Steel Research, 2020, Vol. 167. ISSN 0143-974X.
7. **CEN.** *Eurocode 3- Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints.* Brussels : European Committee for Standardization (CEN), 2005.
8. *Physical properties of high-strength bolt materials at elevated temperatures.* **Pang X-P., Hu Y., Tang S-L., Xiang Z., Wu G., Xu T. and Wang X-Q.** s.l. : Results in Physics, 2019, Vol. 13.
9. *On fracture locus in the equivalent strain and stress triaxiality space.* **Bao. Y. and Weirzbicki, T.** s.l. : International Journal of Mechanical Sciences , 2004, Vol. 46.